

Social Change in the Scheduled Caste Lois of Manipur

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Abstract

Social change is the change in established patterns of social relations, changes in social values, or changes in structures and subsystems operating in society. Social change may be partial or total, though mostly it is partial. No social system ever changes in toto. In other words, social change is always or mostly partial. Contemporary society is changing rapidly. This change is taking place both in its structure and functioning. Likewise, the Manipuri society as other social structures, is also always in the process of change. The *Lois*, the outcast section of the Hinduised Manipuri society during the native rule, is now no more an outcast or marginalised section of the Manipuri society. The paper is an attempt to study the various changes in the Manipuri society which help in the de-marginalisation of this section of the Manipuri society.

1. Concept: Social Change

Change is the law of nature. There is truer about human society. Changes take place in the physical as well as social world. The society that was there 200 years ago is not to be seen today. The transformation that has taken place is the result of change. This change takes place in various forms. (Singh, 1995) Social change is one of such various forms of change. The meaning of social change has been taken differently by different sociologists. According to some sociologists, whenever there is a change in social relationships, we call it 'social change'. While others think that whenever there is a change in any aspect of society, we term it 'social change'. Prof. K.L. Sharma, (1997) writes "The concept of social change is a very broad one. It consists of a constellation of various processes of change in social structure in terms of place, time, and context..... Its pattern and factors may vary from time to time and from place to place. Change can be seen in terms of the elements of time and history to a given society or social phenomena." (Sharma, 1996) In short, social change refers to any change in social relationships in a given society.

2. Background of the Paper:

The Manipuri social identity, since the ancient period, is characterized by moderation, liberation, and fraternity. It is not agreeable to social extremity due to disregard for human dignity and integrity. To a Meitei, there is no question of discrimination against Muslims, Hill people, and low-born people on the grounds of creed, sex, race, and caste. He can inter-dine with all these people. He can go hand in hand and mix them without any bias and prejudice. Love, friendship, and fraternity prevailed in the society. The Meitei society is free from restricting intermarriage with other tribes and communities, except inter-clan (of the same clan) marriage. (Indrakumar, 2002) There was no clear-cut division of hill people and the plain people in Manipur as ancient books tell us a mixing of them alike. Some of the people, who came with Poireiton – a contemporary of Nongda Lairen Pakhangba, first King of Manipur- became hill tribes. (Singh, 1980)

At the same time, many Brahmins came to Manipur. But they were not strong enough to remain as caste Hindus. But there is no history that these minorities suffered in any way at the hands of the majority community. As a matter of fact, instead of being oppressed they were made Manipuri and given status and place amongst the Manipuri society. (Singh, 1987) They were made an integral part of Manipuri society though not part of the *salai*¹(clans in Manipuri words) structure. (Brara, 1988)

The situation came into a dramatic change in Manipuri society, after the mass acceptance of Hinduism by the Meiteis. Then, the Manipuri society was divided into Meitei Hindus, Bamons or Manipuri Brahmins, and *Lois*², the outcast section of Manipuri society during the native rule in Manipur. Manipuri Brahmins used to perform the Hindu rites and rituals. The majority of the Meiteis considered themselves to be Kshatriyas i.e., Meitei Hindus. The *Lois* was the outcaste section of the Manipuri society. They were entitled to be considered Kshatriyas after undergoing some ceremonies of an initiatory nature (Singh, 1980) which was known as Lagoon Thangba i.e., receiving the thread of Kshatriya. (McCulloch, 1982) However, the *Lois* of *Chakpa*³, one of the earliest settlers of Manipur, continued to profess their traditional religion. So, they were treated as an outcast section of the Meitei society. In the recent past, the *Lois* were looked down upon and kept apart from the mainstream of the Meitei Hindu population. At the same time, intermarriage and co-dining with the *Lois* was strictly prohibited. They were treated as a low caste section of the Manipuri society even after Manipur merged into the Union of India on the 15th of October 1949. Such social ostracism of the *Lois* was mainly spearheaded by the orthodox Meitei Hindus. (Chaoba, 1993) So, the *Lois* was looked down upon by some sections of the orthodox Meitei Hindu families. They tried to maintain a distance from them. They also forbid inter-dining, intermarriage between the Meitei Hindus and the *Lois* as well as free mixing between the members of the two communities. Generally, the *Lois* were treated as a subdued caste or lower section of the Meitei society. However, these days, this low social status of the *Lois* – now *Lois* is one of the Scheduled Caste communities recognised by the Government under the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes Amendment Act, 1956 – is gradually disappearing due to many factors especially continuous social change in Manipuri society. In the future, it may disappear from our society.

3. Objectives of the Paper:

In light of the above-mentioned facts, the present paper is an earnest attempt to study by focusing main areas of social change in the Scheduled Caste *Loi* community of Manipur.

4. Data and Methodology:

For the collection of information relating to social change in the Scheduled Caste *Loi* community, both primary and secondary sources are used. To understand the changing social norms in the Manipuri society, especially amongst the Scheduled Caste *Loi* community, the observation method and interview method are applied by participating in the socio-religious ceremonies of the Scheduled Caste *Loi* community. Other secondary sources like books and other printed materials are also used for the study.

Here, it should be noted that the generic term *Lois* originated from the word *Chakpas* who were the earlier settlers of the valley of Manipur before they were subdued by the Meitei Kings. So, whenever any word is used as *Lois* / *Chakpas* / *Chakpa Lois*/ Scheduled Caste *Lois* in any part of this paper, the meaning of the words is the same for this paper.

5. Social Change in the Scheduled Caste *Loi* Community of Manipur:

The major areas of social change taking place in the Scheduled Caste *Loi* community are vividly discoursed under the following heads:

a. Changes in Social Status:

The *Chakpa Lois* have been people of distinct ethnic identities. The Meitei Kings made them their dependent tributary subjects. The term '*Lois*' was, therefore, first applied to that category of people regarding their dependent status under the lordship of the Meitei Kings. (Singh, 1994) Therefore, it is logical to conclude that in the earlier period, the *Lois* enjoyed equal status with the Meiteis. They sometimes tried to assert their independent political status against the Meitei Kings

whom they later tried to subjugate them. There were many records of Meitei Kings sending expeditions to the *Loi* villages when they defied the Meitei Kings. Such expeditions of the Meitei Kings clearly show that the Meitei did not want to tolerate their independence. Thus, they accepted the dominance of the Meiteis.

In the later period, the status of the *Chakpa Lois* was degraded due to many factors. The most important factor was the sending of those people who committed crimes such as adultery, theft, incestuous relationships, etc., and disobeying the orders of the King to *Loi* villages as a punishment. The descendants of such people also became *Lois*. *Loi* villages, thus, became the places of settlement for those people who committed crimes and defied the orders of the King. Such *Loi* communities were ostracized by the Meitei Hindus for they did not adopt Hinduism and did not follow the Meitei Hindus' way of life. However, M. Kirti observed that their degradation in social status is not due to their occupation but to their mode of eating and clothing. (Singh, 1980)

The *Loi* population was considered so inferior that the name Meiteis was not given to them. This social excommunication was applied to intermarriage and co-dining with the *Panna* Meiteis, (*Panna* was an administrative division of the ancient Meitei Kingdom). This social segregation became more sharpened as it partook of ritual character in the wake of mass acceptance of Hinduism by the *Panna* Meiteis in the 18th century and there developed concomitantly a system of attitudes by which the *Lois*, who remained unconverted, were treated as untouchables or at least, near untouchables. (Singh, 1994) The socio-political status of *Lois*, thus lowered.

It was recorded that they would become Meiteis again, provided they gave up their *Lois*' habits of food and drink. This naturally compelled them to give up the manufacture of country liquor. (Hodson, 1989) At one time, they could become *Panna* Meiteis if the King was pleased. (Singh, 1949) Again they were entitled to consideration to be Meitei Kshatriyas after undergoing some ceremonies of an initiating nature. (Singh, 1980) Then, they professed Vainavism with the consent of the King. Thus, the religious policy of the Meitei Kings under the influence of Hinduism has already brought many of the *Loi* villages within the fold of Hinduism. (Singh, 1994) The adoption of the Meitei Hindus' way of life made their social condition much improved. However, despite their conversion into Meitei '*Panna*' and then Hinduism, they were not permitted intermarriage with the girls of the Meiteis. In this regard also, if the King pleased, a low section of the society might marry the daughter of a King as done by King Garibniwaz. (Singh, 1949)

The *Chakpa Lois*, even recently, was looked down upon by some sections of the orthodox Meitei Hindu families. They try to maintain a distance from them. They also forbid inter-dining, inter-marriage between the Meiteis and the *Lois* as well as free mixing between the members, of the two communities. Generally, the *Loi* community is treated as a subdued caste or lower section of the Meitei society. However, nowadays low social status of *Lois* is gradually disappearing. In future, it may totally disappear from our society because of such reasons, namely (a) the Meitei Hindus have gradually abandoned their rigid attitude of social segregation and allowed intermixing, inter-dining and performing of intermarriage with the *Chakpa Lois* ; (b) many of the *Loi* villages have adopted some of the Hindu rituals on the ceremonial occasions in their social life; (c) the present democratic system based on the principles of equality, fraternity, etc. have brought about scientific outlook

among the Meiteis and the *Chakpa Lois*, dramatically; (d) western education fosters liberal ideas in the minds of the Meiteis and the *Chakpa Lois*; and (e) the migration of *Lois* from their native villages to the urban areas, and the Meiteis to many *Loi* villages in search of their livelihood, governmental jobs, etc. also helped in achieving the present changing trends of *Lois*' socio-political status. So, when the Parliamentary Committee on the Welfare of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes visited Manipur in 1984, it reported, "There are certain classes of people who are known as Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes and Other Backward Classes in Manipur. Due to certain religious and social disabilities in ancient times, the above classes of people were considered inferior and untouchables in the Meitei Hindu society. Fortunately, the social evil of untouchability has now disappeared completely." (Visit of Study Group I of Parliamentary Committee, 1984)

b. Changes in the Marriage System:

There were some peculiarities regarding marriage in *Chakpa Loi* community in the early period. They had their own marriage rules. Regarding *Lois*' marriage, Hodson observes, "The *Lois* is divided into clans in much the same way as that of the Meiteis and intermarry with other *Loi* villages if the industry of those villages is identical with that of their own. Thus, the *Lois* of the salt-making villages would intermarry, but it is not likely that they would not go to Phayeng, a silk village, for wives, nor that Phayeng would give them their girls. (Hudson, 1989) They prefer endogamous marriage in their communities. However, they do not allow marriage within the same clan. If such marriage sometimes happens, the families involved are outcasted from the village forever. Even today, inter-clan marriage is strictly prohibited. Such strict observance of the marriage system enabled them to maintain their unique traditional cultures. So, in the early period, the marriage of a *Chakpa* boy or girl with the Meitei localities was non-existent mainly due to (a) difference in socio-religious differences between the *Chakpa Lois* and the Meitei, (b) Those Meiteis who married a *Loi* girl or boy were ex-communicated by the Meitei Hindus and their families were also expelled from their localities.

Traditionally, the marriage of *Chakpa* boy and a *Chakpa* girl took place through the engagement process. Marriage through elopement was strictly forbidden. If such elopement took place in a *Chakpa Loi* village, the couples would be outcasted from the village. However, later on, it was gradually accepted by the *Chakpa Loi* community as the Meitei society also slowly accepted such marriage.

The traditional system of *Chakpa Loi* marriage, as told by the *Chakpa Loi* elders, was very simple and quite different from the marriage of Meitei Hindus. In this system of marriage, the bridegroom party would come to the house of the bride and the bridegroom would sit at the *Phamel* (the south side of the house of the bride). There was no garlanding between the bride and the bridegroom and the bride did not use *Potloi* (a dress used at present during the marriage ceremony of both the Meitei as well as the *Chakpa Lois*). Instead of '*Potloi*' they used a simple dress of *phaneks* i.e., loin clothes. The bride and the bridegroom would present flowers to the audience in the marriage ceremony. This was known as *Lei-Langba*. After that, the newly married couple as a show of respect, bowed to the elders present there. Thus, the traditional marriage ceremony came to an end. In a later period, a marriage ceremony was held at the *Sumang* (courtyard of the house) of the bride.

Changes in the marriage system slowly crept into the *Chakpa Loi* villages especially after the merger of Manipur into the Indian Union on the 15th of October 1949, as it paved the way for a liberal outlook among the people living in the State. The marriage system on the line of the Meitei Hindus also slowly began to be practiced by some *Chakpa Loi* families. Among the *Chakpa Loi* villages, it was first adopted in Leimaram village. In Phayeng village, it was first ceremonised in the early 1950s at the marriage of Ningthoujam Khunjao Singh and Ningthoujam Ongbi Manglemton Devi, the parent of N.Biren Singh, Ex-MLA of the Sekmai Constituency. Although it was ceremonised on the line of Meitei Hindus, there was no Brahmin to perform the marriage ceremony. Instead of Brahmin, it was done by a local Phayeng Pandit. This system is still practiced by most of the *Chakpa Loi* villages.

Changes in the marriage system further arose, after Christianity appeared in the *Chakpa Loi* villages. Those Christianised *Chakpa Lois* wanted to marry their sons or daughters in Christian custom at church. The sons and daughters of Angom Parom Singh,⁴ the first Christian convert of Manipur, and their descendants' marriages were performed at churches. Among the present Christian converts in the Phayeng village, Angom Mohari Singh of Phayeng Makha Leikai, was the first one who ceremonised his two daughters' marriages purely on Christian tradition at church. In Kwatha village, since the early 1960s, marriages of all Christian converts have been performed at churches as the newly wedded couples are generally Christians (one of the partners is generally from the surrounding hill tribes). Thus, changes in the marriage system of the *Chakpa Loi* villages slowly occurred due to the changes in the religious beliefs among the various sections of the *Chakpa Loi* community.

c. Changes in the Family Structure:

The *Chakpa Loi* community, like the Meitei community, is also 'monogamous' and patriarchal in character. From the early period, the *Chakpa* community had a joint family system where the father was the head of the family. Every member of the family obeyed him with fear and due respect. The parent had the sole responsibility for the administration of family affairs. They looked after their children with love and care.

With time, the concept of a joint family has gradually declined and the concept of a nucleus family system is emerging. The changing scenario indicates that a separate family system is also established before the death of their parents. Parents have also accepted the idea of a separate family system if they are required to do so. When the father dies, his eldest son with the consent of his mother, inherits the position and authority enjoyed by his father.

However, at present not only the father but also all adult members of every family used to work for the development of the family. Women are also working in different institutions or offices at various places for earning. They also work in the small-scale cottage industries at home or in their localities. However, the majority of the *Chakpa Lois* are still in their traditional occupations such as cultivation, weaving, distillation of country wine, etc. So, the changing pattern of occupations slowly changes the family structure of *Chakpa Loi* villages.

d. Changes in Education:

Since the introduction of modern education in Manipur in the late 1880s and vigorous efforts on the parts of the Missionaries and the State Authorities, there was little interest in education among the people of Manipur including the *Chakpa Lois*. People considered learning modern education impure (*Mangba* in Manipuri). So, there were separate dresses for learning. The students had to keep their dresses and books outside their houses in a separate place especially at *Mamang Sangoi* (a front-courtyard house specially built for every house of the Meitei) after returning from school. They had to enter their houses after bathing and changing into new dresses. As a result of this feeling of untouchability, no English school could flourish in the soil of Manipur for a considerable length of time. (Devi, 2001) Though the Manipuris remained till the beginning of the 20th century, very indifferent to the modern system of education they were not uncultured. So, B.C. Allen writes, “They are well dressed, well housed, and clever craftsmen. Men and women alike are full of enterprise and intelligence, and few people manage better without schooling than the Manipuris.” (Allen, 2002)

There was rapid expansion in education especially primary education after Manipur became a Part C State of the Indian Union. Many primary schools were established in many parts of Manipur including the *Chakpa Loi* villages. However, the facilities given to Scheduled Caste students were not available to the *Chakpa Loi* students during this period as they became the Scheduled Castes only after the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Modification) Order, 1956 was passed. Then, the era of educational enlightenment heightened among the *Chakpa Loi* villages where its foundation was laid first, with the establishment of a Lower Primary School at Sekmai in 1893. During this period, there was no restriction on the Scheduled Castes or Scheduled Tribes in admission to educational institutions. So, it can be said that education was secularised in Manipur. The educated people irrespective of caste and social background got new avenues of upward mobility in the traditional somewhat rigid social structure in Manipur. So, education began to play a significant role in the process of modernization of the Manipuri society. The changes brought by the education system led to the growth of a new intelligentsia or intellectual section among the *Chakpa Lois* led by Kh. Chaoba Singh of Sekmai, was the first *Chakpa Loi* leader who had dedicated his life to the welfare of the *Chakpa* community. They led the *Chakpa Lois* to the path of modernity by highlighting the usefulness of learning various provisions of the Constitution of India for the welfare of the Scheduled Castes. In other words, it can be said that education plays a crucial role in the socialization of the younger generation and is an important intervening variable in social change in Manipur particularly among the *Chakpa Lois*. Thus, modern education brought a wave of change in the social values in Manipur. People began to the idea of liberal humanism brought by the new education and they began not only to appreciate it but also to adapt their lives to the changing environment. After this, the old taboos started declining. (Devi,2001) So with the development of modern education, the earlier social stigma given on low caste Lois by high caste Meiteis slowly disappeared in the modern Manipuri society. So, the Report of the Commissioner for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes 1958-59 says, “The States of Assam and Kerala and the Union Territories of Tripura and Manipur, feel that such lists (list of villages where untouchability is being practiced) were hardly necessary because the problem is far from acute in their areas.” (Shrikant, 1959) The same Report of the Commissioner doubted the claims of the above-mentioned States and the Union Territories. So, it writes, “That in Assam, West Bengal, Manipur, and Tripura there is no untouchability is too tall a claim to be taken at its face value. (Shrikant, 1959) However, as far as Manipur is concerned, there is no practice of

untouchability. In all the reports of the Parliamentary Committee on the Welfare of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes which visited Manipur said that there was no practice of untouchability in Manipur. For example, one such report says, “Although the problem of untouchability has disappeared, the provision of Untouchability (Offense) Act, 1955 are enforced in the State to ensure that any attempt by any section of people to revive untouchability is eradicated at the infant stage.” (Visit of Study Group I of Parliamentary Committee, 1984) The achievements of such a stage of social harmony in Manipur particularly in the minds of the *Chakpa Lois* are due to the enlightened conscience of the people. At the same time, many educated and employed *Chakpa Lois* have been settling in the Imphal area and thereby intermixed with the Meitei Hindus without any inferiority complex. The local Meitei Hindus also treat them equally without any discrimination. Thus, it further accelerates the social harmony between the *Chakpa Lois* and the Meitei Hindus.

The Centre as well as the State Governments has also been giving scholarships to the students of Scheduled Castes of Manipur to improve education and to give incentives to the Scheduled Castes students to excel further in their respective fields of higher studies. In other words, it can be said that the progress of literacy and education especially in higher education and professional training among the *Chakpa Loi* community, is often responsible for changing employment and occupational patterns. It also accelerates the mobility of the *Chakpa loi* population. The development of education of the *Chakpa Loi* community is also responsible for fostering their social consciousness and traditional values in Manipuri society. Due to modern education, now, it can be said that the *Chakpa Loi* community does not have an inferiority complex to Meitei Hindus. Thus, under the impact of the development of modern education, the social relations in Manipur especially the Meiteis vis-a-vis the *Chakpa Lois* take a new form with suitable modifications.

e. Social Mobility among Scheduled Caste Lois:

It is seen that people in society continue to move up and down the status scale due to changes in the capabilities of individuals or groups from one social class or social stratum to another. This movement is called social mobility. (Bhusan & Sachdeva, 1988) There are various types of social mobility. The type of social mobility found in the *Chakpa Loi* community like the Manipuri society is open system mobility. It means that there occur status changes for the individuals based on their accomplishments. The most important reason for social mobility in the *Chakpa Loi* community is getting employment with a family member of the community either in a public or private sector. One of the ways by which occupational mobility facilitates social mobility for the immediate members of the family is by helping them to get a better education and employment. It is now a well-established fact that a member of the *Chakpa Loi* community already in employment acts as one of the chief sources of information concerning employment opportunities in his community. Now in every *Chakpa Loi* village, there are information centres which may be a club or other organizations to promote employment opportunities for people of their village and community. This indicates that there is a strong commitment among the *Chakpa Lois* to improve their social and economic conditions. Such commitment manifests not only individual mobility but also group mobility. However, it is only the individual mobility through which the social standing of a person is held in high esteem by the community.

The process of social mobility in the *Chakpa* community has been accelerated by the removal of traditional and ritual sanctions by the Meitei Hindus. It is also influenced by modern education and taking up new occupations in the professional and administrative areas. At present, there are various scopes to improve their status as well as their standard of living. Many *Chakpa Loi* youths are now pursuing various professional lines. In other words, it can be said that they generally started giving up their traditional occupations by pursuing the new occupations that have arisen in recent times based on their standard of education and training. However, the vast majority of the uneducated section of the *Chakpa Loi* community is still pursuing their traditional occupations. They are also doing petty businesses like opening grocery shops, roadside hotels, pan dukan, and others to improve their economy.

Another process of social mobility found in the *Chakpa Loi* community is the trend of migration to the urban areas started by some families from all the *Chakpa Loi* villages. However, the rate of migration is very low. The main reasons for starting the migration to the urban areas among the *Chakpa Lois* are to get higher education for their children, increase occupational mobility, desire for a higher standard of living, and escape from unwanted elements found in their respective villages especially underground related problems. The migration among the *Chakpa Lois* is also necessitated due to the present transfer and posting system in Manipur as far as the Government employed *Chakpa Lois* is concerned. The trend of migration of the *Chakpa Lois* is also very interesting because those who want to urban areas (generally in the Imphal area) where the transport and communication system can easily be available with their respective villages. For example, those *Chakpa Lois* from Andro village generally favour migrating Wangkhei and nearby areas as their bus station is at Wangkhei, a place in Imphal city having a big bus station generally known as the 'Andro Parking' which serves as the nearest bus station to Imphal from Andro. Likewise, the people coming from Leimaram, a *Chakpa* village generally settle at Ningthemkon of Kwakeithel (F.C Godown Road).

It is noteworthy to highlight that they are not mistreated by the neighbours of their respective newly settled areas even though they are coming from the *Chakpa Loi* villages. Such social harmony is there, at present, as there is no question of socio-religious discrimination on any ground in Manipur. Thus, the rate of social mobility in the *Chakpa Loi* community is slowly increasing vis-a-vis the Meitei Hindu society.

Conclusion:

Social change is a universal phenomenon. So, the society that was there was there 2000 years ago is not to see today. This fact is true for the Scheduled Caste Lois – formerly *Lois/ Chakpa Lois* of Manipur. They were, during the native rule in Manipur, treated as outcast sections of the Meitei society and were kept a distance from the Meitei Hindus. They were also forbidden inter-marriage, and inter-dining with the Meitei Hindus. The situation came into a speedy change after the introduction of modern education in Manipur and Manipur became a part of the Union of India. So, nowadays, this low social status of the Scheduled Caste Lois is gradually disappearing. In future, it may totally disappear from our society mainly from the following grounds, namely (i) the Meitei Hindus have gradually abandoned their rigid attitude of social segregation and allowed intermixing, inter-dining and performing of intermarriage with the Scheduled Caste *Lois* ; (ii) many of the

Scheduled Caste *Loi* villages have adopted some of the Hindu rituals on the ceremonial occasions in their social life; (iii) the present democratic system of India which is based to establish social, economic and political justice, liberty of thought, expression, belief and worship, equality of status and opportunity and fraternity etc. have brought about rational outlook among the Meiteis and the Scheduled Caste *Lois*, dramatically; (iv) introduction of western education fosters liberal ideas in the minds of the Meiteis and the *Chakpa Lois*; and (v) the migration of Scheduled Caste *Lois* from their native villages to the urban areas, and the Meiteis to many Scheduled Caste *Loi* villages in search of their livelihood, governmental jobs etc. also helped in achieving the present trend of social change in the Scheduled Caste *Lois* of Manipur.

Notes:

1. Generally, *salai* corresponds to a clan, the members of which regard them as being descended from a common ancestor.
2. *Lois* was the subdued and lower section of the Meitei society during the native rule in Manipur. *Lois*, at present, is one of the seven Scheduled Caste Communities of Manipur.
3. *Chakpas* were earlier settlers of the valley of Manipur long before the Meiteis came to settle in this valley of Manipur.
4. Angom Porom Singh of *Loi* village of Chakpa Phayeng was the first Christian convert of Manipur He was baptised by Rev. William Pettigrew on the 3rd January 1896 at a place called 'Mongba Hanba Laipham' now known as the Mahaballi Temple on the bank of the Imphal River.

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